
Deliverable D-JRP- TOXOSOURCES-WP2.2

**Report on quantitative
exposure data
from survey of WP2
Workpackage 2 of
JRP22-FBZ4.1-
TOXOSOURCES**

Responsible Partners:
RIVM, SSI

GENERAL INFORMATION

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D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP2.2

REPORT ON QUANTITATIVE EXPOSURE DATA FROM SURVEY OF WP2

BACKGROUND

This is a public deliverable of One Health EJP Joint Research Project:

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES – *Toxoplasma gondii* sources quantified

(<https://onehealthjep.eu/jrp-toxosources/>);

Work Package:

JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP2 Multicentre quantitative microbiological risk assessment for *T. gondii* infections;

Task:

JRP-TOXOSOURCES- WP2-T3 Quantitative exposure survey.

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TOXOSOURCES addresses the research question – **What are the relative contributions of the different sources of *T. gondii* infection?** – by using several multidisciplinary approaches and novel and improved methods to yield robust estimates that can inform risk management and policy makers.

TOXOSOURCES WP2 estimates the relative contribution of different sources of *T. gondii* infection by quantitative microbiological risk assessment (QMRA). Objectives of TOXOSOURCES WP2:

- ✓ To estimate the relative contribution of food and environmental transmission routes (T1)
- ✓ To provide an overview of the prevalence in food animals and cats (T2)
- ✓ To quantify human exposure to possible sources of infection (T3)
- ✓ To provide an overview of the processing parameters for relevant meat products (T4)
- ✓ To provide an overview of prevalence and risk factors of human infection (T5)

To help achieve the goals of TOXOSOURCES WP2, within task WP2-T3 a consumer survey was carried out to collect harmonized exposure data specifically for QMRA purposes. The task was performed successfully, all related Milestones were reached on time, and related data sharing between WPs and tasks of TOXOSOURCES consortium was efficient. This Deliverable reports on the work done and highlights selected observations and the key achievements of the process.

PURPOSE

The aim of the work was to collect data suitable for quantitative microbial risk assessment (QMRA) from nine European countries, representing all four European regions, in a harmonized way. Questions were tailored to capture behaviors and exposures relevant for *Toxoplasma gondii* infections. Since this zoonotic parasite can be transmitted via meat of infected animals, contaminated vegetables and soil exposure, the data will also be useful for QMRAs of many other pathogens sharing similar transmission routes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Based on previous experience with a questionnaire to collect data for QMRA purposes (Chardon and Swart 2016), a questionnaire was developed by scientists from nine European countries in collaboration with a market research agency (GfK). The questionnaire with 34 multiple-choice questions was translated in nine languages and distributed among consumer panels in the Czech Republic, Denmark, France, Germany, the Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, and Spain. The targeted number of respondents by country was 2,000, except for Denmark and Norway, which targeted 3,000 respondents each. The sample was drawn representative of region. Respondents completed the questionnaire between April 23 and May 17, 2021. Respondents answered questions on the frequency of consumption and portion sizes for a range of meat products (including country-specific products) and raw vegetables, on specific risk behavior such as tasting raw meat and drinking unpasteurized milk, on heating preferences, storage conditions and washing of vegetables, and on buying organic meat and ready-to-eat vegetables.

For comparability with other data, the selection of product categories was based on the EFSA Foodex2 database (European Food Safety Authority, 2015). This database offers a standardized classification of foodstuff, at varying levels of detail. The baseline level used was seven, which is the most detailed level. Products always cooked before consumption were considered not to present a risk of *T. gondii* infection and therefore excluded from the questionnaire. Moreover, some categories were split by animal species (e.g. fresh meat cuts), whereas other categories were merged (e.g. sprouts and shoots) as they were considered similar in risk of *T. gondii* contamination and consumption style. Both general and country-specific examples were provided for each category. In addition, for each country we included country-specific meat products of expected high risk to be asked separately.

After the survey, the data were weighted by age, gender and education level based on Eurostat data. A harmonized urbanity measure was constructed, to be included in the weighting, as consumption habits can vary between rural and urban areas. Raw data including weights were delivered by GfK to RIVM in an SPSS file. Data were imported to R for visualization and data analysis. Bayesian statistics were employed to derive probability distributions for each question pertaining to consumption frequencies and portion sizes, to facilitate use of this information in the QMRA.

SELECTED RESULTS AND HIGHLIGHTS

The age distribution of respondents compared to Eurostat data is presented in Fig. 1. The gender distribution was quite even (47.0% to 52.7% males). Depending on the country, low education level was underrepresented in the survey (Fig. 2). The harmonized urbanity measure (Fig. 3) was constructed at the postal code level based on a land cover indicator (using the Corine Land Cover raster dataset from Copernicus) and a population density indicator (using the population density raster dataset from GISCO).

Figure 1 Cumulative age distribution by country for respondents in survey (blue) compared to Eurostat data (red). In the survey, age was asked in 10-year age categories for adults, with the highest category 70 years and older.

Figure 2 Education level by country for respondents in the survey compared to Eurostat data (target).

Source: GADM.

Figure 3 Harmonized urbanity measure per postal code

Most respondents did not reportedly adhere to any specific diet (Fig. 4). The proportion following vegetarian diet varied from 2.5% (Norway) to 6.8% (Germany), whilst vegan diet was reported by 1.2% (the Czech Republic) to 2.5% (Germany) of the respondents.

Figure 4 Frequency of reported adherence to specific diets by country. As it was possible to select multiple diets, respondents may have been included more than once and the fractions do not necessarily represent the percentage of adherence to the diet in the sampled population.

Data on the frequency of consumption for different meat products (e.g. sausage, in Fig. 5) and raw and unpeeled fruits and vegetables (e.g. tomato, in Fig. 6), as well as exposure to soil (Fig. 7) showed apparent differences by country.

Figure 5 Frequency of sausage consumption by country

Figure 6 Frequency of tomato consumption by country

Figure 7 Frequency of soil contact by country.

Beta distributions were fitted to the cumulative frequency data (Fig. 8). Product specific beta distributions will be used as input in the QMRA model.

Figure 8 Cumulative frequency of consumption for sausage (black line) and fitted beta distribution (green line) (all countries). From the graph it can be read, for example, that sausage is consumed less than once per four days (0.25/day) by approximately 75% (0.75) of the consumers.

Regarding the amount the consumers typically consume when eating meat cuts, meatballs and sausages, estimated by them choosing between pictures reflecting different portion sizes, it was concluded that the average portion size was 132.0 g, with somewhat lower averages for sausages and meatballs, and higher for meat cuts (Fig. 9).

Figure 9 Mean portion size for all meat combined in grams (left), and how meat cuts, meatballs and sausages deviate from this mean (right). Distributions represent uncertainty. For example, on average, sausages have portion sizes of a bit more than 1 gram less than a random meat product, which is 132 grams.

In addition to consumption frequencies and portion sizes, information on specific habits from farm-to-fork that can influence the risk of *T. gondii* infection are important. For example, freezing meat is important as this may inactivate *T. gondii* tissue cysts (Kotula, Dubey et al. 1991). Meat was purchased frozen more frequently in Portugal and Spain compared to other countries (Fig. 10), whereas storage in the freezer appeared to differ less between countries. Like freezing, heating may inactivate *T. gondii* tissue cysts (Dubey, Kotula et al. 1990). Preparation preferences differed by country for the different categories of meat products (Fig. 11). Because animals with outdoor access have a higher risk of *T. gondii* infection (Stelzer, Basso et al. 2019), the differences in frequency of purchasing free range and organic meat are of interest (Fig. 12).

Figure 10 Frequency of frozen meat purchase by country.

Figure 11 Preparation styles for meat cuts, minced meat products other than sausages (e.g. hamburgers) and sausages by country.

Figure 12 Frequency of organic/free range meat purchase by country

Foodborne transmission of *T. gondii* via ingestion of oocysts on fresh produce is under-recognized compared to foodborne transmission via meat (Shapiro, Bahia-Oliveira et al. 2019). Consequently, less information has been available on factors that may influence foodborne transmission via fruits and vegetables. The new information from this survey e.g. on purchase of ready-to-eat products (Fig. 12) thus contributes in filling in a relevant knowledge gap, together with other work done in TOXOSOURCES. Ready-to-eat products are the focus of TOXOSOURCES WP3.

Figure 12 Frequency of purchasing ready-to-eat vegetables by country

DISCUSSION AND PERSPECTIVES

A consumer survey addressing the risk of *T. gondii* infection was successfully carried out in nine European countries. The distribution over age categories, gender and education levels in the survey deviated from Eurostat data, although statistical analysis still needs to be performed. This information, in addition to the distribution over different urbanity categories are used to construct a weighting variable. It needs to be emphasized that the unweighted results for questions on exposure do not necessarily reflect exposure in the total population. Both weighted and unweighted results will be compared between countries and to data available in the EFSA FoodEx2 database. The data will be used as input for multi-country QMRA modelling, and for that purpose, distributions have been fitted to frequency and portion size data.

The work and its results are of interest to the scientific community and policy makers, also to those working on other pathogens that share similar transmission routes. Results and data are planned to be disseminated in an open access peer-reviewed publication with the raw and weighted survey data and the fitted distributions provided as supplementary information.

DISSEMINATION AND IMPACT

The work was performed successfully as an international collaboration of scientists from public health, animal health and food safety institutes, and the complementary expertise in the multidisciplinary TOXOSOURCES consortium proved useful in the process. During the whole process, regular meetings were organized to discuss the work, and the experiences were shared especially with TOXOSOURCES-WP3. The work included integrative aspects in terms of collaboration and harmonizing the process, and cross-sectoral aspects in terms of collaboration within the consortium, in particular with WP3. Capacity-building and training aspects were also included, and both experienced and early-career scientists participated in the work.

This work is an excellent example of efficient sharing of results within the TOXOSOURCES consortium to enable synergies and timely use of the results. A list of fresh produce selected from literature review (D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP3.5) and at risk to be contaminated by *T. gondii* oocysts was provided by WP3-T2 (Milestone M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-06) to develop the questionnaires for this work. A list of meat products was provided by WP2-T4 (Milestone M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-04). Data have been used to identify relevant meat products for WP2-T4 (Milestone M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-12) and provided as input to WP2-T1 for the QMRA (Milestone M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-13).

Dissemination of the outcomes is ongoing in collaboration with TOXOSOURCES WP1 and following the FAIR principles. The work and its results are being prepared for peer-reviewed scientific publication and the manuscript will be submitted to an Open Access journal. The survey's methods and results were summarized into a conference abstract 'Consumer habits in nine European countries captured to assess the risk of foodborne infections', which was selected for a poster presentation at the ONE 2022 Conference (21-24 June, Brussels). Presenter: Marieke Opsteegh.

This work yielded a unique overview of exposure behavior relevant for *T. gondii* infections in Europe, and as input for the assessment of source attribution, these data can aid the development of effective prevention strategies. In addition to scientific impact, societal impact is expected.

REFERENCES

- Chardon, J. and A. Swart (2016). "Food Consumption and Handling Survey for Quantitative Microbiological Consumer Phase Risk Assessments." J Food Prot **79**(7): 1221-1233.
- Dubey, J. P., A. W. Kotula, A. Sharar, C. D. Andrews and D. S. Lindsay (1990). "Effect of high temperature on infectivity of *Toxoplasma gondii* tissue cysts in pork." J Parasitol **76**(2): 201-204.
- European Food Safety Authority, E. F. S. (2015). "The food classification and description system FoodEx 2 (revision 2)." EFSA Supporting Publications **12**(5): 804E.
- Kotula, A. W., J. P. Dubey, A. K. Sharar, C. D. Andrews, S. K. Shen and D. S. Lindsay (1991). "Effect of freezing on infectivity of *Toxoplasma gondii* tissue cysts in pork." Journal of Food Protection **54**(9): 687-690.
- Shapiro, K., L. Bahia-Oliveira, B. Dixon, A. Dumètre, L. A. de Wit, E. VanWormer and I. Villena (2019). "Environmental transmission of *Toxoplasma gondii*: Oocysts in water, soil and food." Food and Waterborne Parasitology **15**: e00049.
- Stelzer, S., W. Basso, J. Benavides Silván, L. M. Ortega-Mora, P. Maksimov, J. Gethmann, F. J. Conraths and G. Schares (2019). "Toxoplasma gondii infection and toxoplasmosis in farm animals: Risk factors and economic impact." Food and Waterborne Parasitology **15**: e00037.